

8th Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society Symposium (IBICS-8)

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Local Organising Committee: Christopher S. Burke (Chair),^a Orla Ni Dhubhghaill,^a Jerry Reen,^a William Daly,^a James Stack,^a Tara McInerney,^a and Rebecca Galway.^a

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Organisation: Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS).

Website: <https://ibics.ie>

Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, CRC Press, MSD, CEM, Particular Sciences, Mason Technology, Accuscience, GPE/Julabo, Scientific Laboratory Supplies (SLS)/Ohaus, Medical Supply Company (MSC).

Summary

The 8th Symposium of the Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS-8) was held at University College Cork on Friday, 6th December 2024. The annual IBICS symposia showcase recent work from researchers who work at the interface of inorganic chemistry and the life sciences, and provides an opportunity for networking between society members and industry representatives. At IBICS-8, over 70

attendees were present, including academics at all levels, from early career researchers to principal investigators, and industry sponsors and exhibitors. Two international plenary speakers headed the scientific programme; Prof. Tatjana Parac-Vogt (KU Leuven) and Dr. Jennifer Cavet (The University of Manchester). Three Ireland-based invited lectures were presented by Prof. Dmitri Papkovsky (UCC), Prof. Andrew Kellett (DCU) and Dr. Joseph Byrne (UCD). Aligned with the spirit of IBICS, the remaining contributions to the symposium came

from early career researchers with several excellent presentations, six flash presentations, and thirteen poster presentations. The event was a huge success, thanks to the strong engagement from our Irish biological inorganic community and the fantastic financial support from industry sponsors.

Attendees

Postgraduate and postdoctoral researchers, academics, and industry exhibitors/representatives made up most of the 70+ attendees at IBICS-8, working diversely across fields of inorganic chemistry and its interface with the life sciences. There was an excellent balance of female and male representation, from across different Irish institutions and beyond, and this was reflected in our symposium programme (Table 1).

Target audience: academics, postgraduate researchers, postdoctoral researchers, early career (academia).

Programme

IBICS-8 was a full one-day event, running from welcome and registration at 10am to closing remarks and reception at 6pm. Across three sessions, the scientific programme comprised eleven oral presentations contributed by two international plenary speakers, three invited Ireland-based speakers, the IBICS Gold Medal Award winner, and five early career researchers. In addition, six flash presentations across two quick-fire sessions showcased a sample of the thirteen poster presentations that were displayed at two designated poster sessions sponsored by the RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section. Each oral and flash session was chaired by a leading academic in the field of bioinorganic chemistry. The IBICS AGM was held during the lunch break of the symposium, and several other short breaks enabled a good opportunity for networking.

Table 1. IBICS-8 Scientific Programme

Time	Speaker and title of presentation
10:00	Registration, coffee and poster setup
10:30	Opening remarks – Dr. Luca Ronconi, IBICS President
Session 1 - Chair: Dr. Orla Ni Dhubhghaill	
10:40	Plenary: Dr. Jennifer S. Cavet (University of Manchester) <i>Metals at the Host-Pathogen Interface: Strategies for Overcoming Metal-Stress in Gastrointestinal Pathogens</i>
11:20	Dr. Joshua McLean (Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland) <i>Design and Synthesis of Clickable E3 Ligase Ligands for Novel Metallo-PROTAC Development</i>
11:35	Ryan Madden (Dublin City University) <i>Ru(II) tris-Heteroleptic Switch-on Probes for Selective Targeting of Pancreatic Cancer</i>
11:50	Invited: Prof. Dmitri Papkovsky (University College Cork) <i>Phosphorescent Metalloporphyrins and Optochemical Sensors for Cell Analysis</i>
12:20	ICI Flash Session 1 - Chair: Dr. Diego Montagner Sponsored by ICI

12:35	Lunch (provided)
12:35	Poster Session 1 Sponsored by RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section
13:25	IBICS Annual General Meeting
Session 2 - Chair: Dr. Jerry Reen	
13:55	Invited: Prof. Andrew Kellett (Dublin City University) <i>Recent Advances in Artificial Gene Editing and DNA Targeted Metallodrug Design</i>
14:25	Ella O'Sullivan (TU Dublin) <i>Investigation of Regulated Cell Death (RCD) Modalities in Novel Copper (II), Manganese (II) and Silver (I) Complexes Containing Dicarboxylate and 1,10-Phenanthroline Ligands</i>
14:40	Frederica Brescia (University of Galway) <i>Design and Development of Gold(III)-Glycoconjugates as Antiviral Agents Against SARS-CoV-2</i>
14:55	Invited: Dr. Joseph Byrne (University College Dublin) <i>Glycoconjugate Metal Complexes as Anti-adhesives against Pathogens</i>
15:25	ICI Flash Session 2 - Chair: Prof. Orla Howe Sponsored by ICI
15:40	Poster Session 2 Sponsored by RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section
Session 3 - Chair: Prof. Michael Devereux	
16:40	Eleanor Windle (University College Dublin) <i>Disaggregation of Metallo-phthalocyanines by Guanine-rich Nucleic Acid Sequences Monitored with Steady-state and Ultrafast Spectroscopies</i>
16:55	Plenary: Prof. Tatjana N. Parac-Vogt (KU Leuven) <i>Artificial Enzymes Based on Metal Oxo-clusters: from Discrete Species to Extended Materials</i>
17:35	IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award Rhianne Curley (Dublin City University) <i>Visualising Stress Granule Dynamics with an RNA Guanine Quadruplex Targeted Ruthenium(II) Peptide Conjugate</i>
17:55	Prize-giving and closing remarks – Dr. Luca Ronconi
18:00	Wine reception

Proceedings

Dr. Christopher Burke (UCC), Chair of the local organising committee, warmly welcomed all attendees to UCC at its Western Gateway Building.

The IBICS president, **Dr. Luca Ronconi** (University of Galway), officially opened the symposium giving an overview of the history of IBICS symposia and the scientific programme to follow.

Session 1 – Chair: Dr. Orla Ni Dhubhghaill (UCC)

Our first international plenary speaker, **Dr. Jennifer Cavet** from The University of Manchester kicked off scientific presentations. Jen's research interests focus on infectious disease,

including to identify and examine the roles of metal homeostasis and metal sensing proteins in a variety of different bacterial pathogens. Her plenary lecture described four research stories centred on copper, zinc, and manganese transporters across different *Salmonella*, *Listeria*, *Campylobacter* and *Helicobacter* bacteria, discussing their associated roles and contributions to infection.

Next, **Dr. Joshua McLean** (RCSI, Griffith research group) presented on proteolysis targeting chimeras (PROTACs) and emerging work on the design and synthesis of ligase ligands that are

amenable to click chemistry with bioactive Pt or Au complexes, including under bioorthogonal conditions. A gold metallo-PROTAC derivative was shown to exhibit high potency under biological evaluation.

Ryan Madden (DCU, Keyes research group) then presented on his work in developing a new light-switching tris-heteroleptic Ru(II) polypyridyl complex that selectively labels human

pancreatic cancer cells for high-contrast fluorescence bioimaging diagnostics. Ryan also described ongoing parallel work on identifying peptide sequences and their target protein receptors that are upregulated following chemotherapy resistance.

Prof. Dmitri Papkovsky (UCC) followed next as our first *invited speaker*. Dmitri is a Professor at the UCC School of Biochemistry and Cell Biology and his research interests include

phosphorescence based probes for sensing and imaging of cell and tissue oxygenation, live FLIM/PLIM microscopy, and their use to study roles of O₂ in biological systems, cell metabolism, bioenergetics and common disease states. His talk discussed his work on photoluminescent porphyrin dye systems as applied for cell analysis, including pH and O₂ sensing and the link

to monitoring oxygen consumption and extracellular acidification rates.

Following lunch and the first poster session, the **IBICS AGM** was held with good attendance from members at the symposium.

Session 2 – Chair: Dr. Jerry Reen (UCC)

Restarting proceedings after the AGM was our second *invited speaker*, **Prof. Andrew Kellett** (DCU), who is Professor of Inorganic and Medicinal Chemistry in the School of Chemical Sciences at

Dublin City University (DCU). His research interests focus on the discovery of metallodrugs, artificial gene editing tools, and DNA damage and repair. Andrew presented new work on artificial metallonuclease scaffolds that are built via click chemistry, including a bioactive C₃-symmetric ligand and its copper complexes that demonstrate capability for therapy through DNA damage.

Next, **Ella O'Sullivan** (TU Dublin, Howe and Devereaux research groups) presented recent work on Cu(II), Mn(II), and Ag(I) complexes bearing dicarboxylate and phenanthroline ligands.

Ella described the relative therapeutic efficacy and differences in mechanisms of action against cancerous and non-cancerous cells based on the metal ion, elucidated from data from several assays and spectroscopic imaging techniques.

Frederica Brescia (University of Galway, Ronconi research group) then presented on a new approach to antiviral therapy using Au(III) glycoconjugates based on a scaffold that uses a

linker bridge between monosaccharides and chemoactive gold (III) dithiocarbamate moieties that are posited to interact with the zinc-finger domain of SARS-CoV-2 papain-like protease.

Dr. Joseph Byrne (UCD) closed out this session as our third *invited speaker*. Joe is a Lecturer in Bioinorganic Chemistry at UCD and his research interests are in glycoscience, inorganic chemistry, luminescence and antimicrobial resistance. Joe communicated some recent research from his team, including Ru(II) glycoclusters with ranging capability to inhibit *P. aeruginosa* biofilms based on the nature of the carbohydrate motif, and approaches to targeting LecA lectin with emissive lanthanide complexes and metal-galactoside derivatives.

Session 3 – Chair: Prof. Mick Devereaux (TU Dublin)

The final session commenced with a presentation from **Eleanor Windle** (UCD, Quinn research group), who described the dual photodynamic therapy and photothermal therapy applications of Zn-phthalocyanine that depends on its aggregation and that can be disrupted by binding to guanine-rich nucleic acid sequences, as examined through a host of steady-state and time-resolved spectroscopic techniques.

The next contribution came from our second international *plenary speaker*, **Prof. Tatjana Parac-Vogt** from the Department of Chemistry at KU Leuven (Belgium). Tatjana's main research lines are the development of metal cluster-based complexes and materials such as polyoxometalates (POMs) and metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) for biologically inspired reactions with biomolecules and model systems. Her group is also creating new hybrid structures based on polyoxometalates using principles of biomolecular recognition and supramolecular chemistry. Accordingly, Tatjana's plenary lecture described her team's work on investigating catalytic MOF nanozyme structures and POM systems with embedded strong Lewis acid metal cations as artificial protease enzymes.

The final oral presentation of the symposium was given by **Rhianne Curley** (DCU, Keyes research group), who is this year's winner of the IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award.

Rhianne's award lecture centred on her recent PhD work on peptide-directed Ru(II) complexes that target RNA G-quadruplexes in live cancer cells to induce stress granule formation, and with capability to image this process via confocal fluorescence microscopy.

ICI Flash Sessions –

Session Chairs: Prof. Orla Howe (TU Dublin) and Dr. Diego Montagner (MU)

Six flash presentations were delivered across two flash presentation sessions, and were delivered by; Agnieszka Kawalerska (TUD), Jack Daly (UCC), Amélia Auville (UCD), Karina Chan (RCSI), Daryl Reidy (MU), and Baile Wu (UCC). All flash presenters also contributed poster presentations to the Poster Sessions.

RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section Poster Sessions

Two poster sessions were held to maximise engagement and networking opportunities. In addition to the flash presenters listed above, poster presentations were also contributed by; Manal Alrashidi (University of Galway), Guilia Ferrari (MU), Judit Fodor (TCD), Conor Newsome (DCU), Stephen O'Sullivan (DCU), James Stack (UCC), and Leila Tabrizi (DCU).

The symposium was closed out by IBICS president, **Dr. Luca Ronconi**, with the presentation of prizes, his farewell address, and an invitation for all to join the wine reception for further discussion on the excellent presentations delivered throughout the symposium.

Figure 1. Presentation of gifts to plenary speakers, Dr. Jen Cavet (left) and Prof. Tatjana Parac-Vogt (right).

Figure 2. Some pictures from the Poster Sessions, including James Stack (Poster 11), Judit Foder (Poster 6), Daryl Reidy (Poster 10), and Stephen O'Sullivan (Poster 9).

Figure 3. Some pictures from across the symposium, including during the scientific programme, the welcome reception, poster sessions and closing wine reception.

Prizes

The **IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal** was this year awarded to **Rhianne Curley** from Dublin City University. Rhianne, who is a final year PhD student under the supervision of Prof. Tia Keyes, focusses her research on the application of novel luminescent charge transfer compounds for live cell imaging and phototherapy, with the goal of advancing both diagnostic and therapeutic technologies. She has presented her work at numerous international conferences, earning presentation awards, and has published in prestigious journals such as *Angewandte Chemie*. The judging committee also recognised **Paul O'Dowd (RCSI) as a Highly Commended Runner-Up**.

The IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal is awarded annually to one PhD student who has distinguished themselves across a range of criteria throughout their PhD with a focus on research performance, achievements and impact in the field of medicinal and biological inorganic chemistry across the island of Ireland. This year, the IBICS award selection committee was impressed by the high standard of applications that this medal continues to attract and strongly encouraged eligible researchers to apply to future competitions.

Figure 4. Dr. Luca Ronconi (IBICS President), presenting Rhianne Curley with the 2024 IBICS Postgraduate Gold Medal Award.

The IBICS president presented three sponsored prizes during the closing remarks of the symposium. Awardees in each category were selected by our independent panel of judges.

Firstly, the **MSD Best Oral Presentation** was awarded to **Ella O'Sullivan** (TU Dublin) who spoke on *Investigation of Regulated Cell Death (RCD) modalities in novel*

Copper(II), Manganese(II) and Silver(I) complexes containing dicarboxylate and 1,10-Phenanthroline ligands. Ella is supervised by Prof. Orla Howe and Prof. Mick Devereaux (both TU Dublin). IBICS is grateful to MSD for their support of this prize as our exclusive silver-tier sponsor at IBICS-8.

Next, the **ICI Flash Prize** for the best flash presentation was awarded to **Karina Chan** from RCSI. Karina, who is supervised by Dr. Darren Griffith (RCSI), provided highlights from her work on the *Development of Pt-PROTACs to degrade Pt-binding Proteins*. As part of her prize, Karina was awarded a copy of *Targeted Metallo-Drugs: Design, Development, and Modes of Action* (Edited by Etelka Farkas & Celine J. Marmion) courtesy of the kind sponsorship of CRC Press - Taylor & Francis Group.

Lastly, the **RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section Best Poster Prize** was awarded to **Jack Daly** from University College Cork for communicating his work on *N,N-disubstituted-N'-acylthiourea metal(II) complexes as use for antifungal agents, the good, the bad, and the molecular geometry*. Jack is supervised by Dr. Davide Tiana and Dr. Dave Otway (both UCC).

Figure 5. RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section Best Poster Prize was awarded to Jack Daly (left) and the ICI Flash Prize for the best flash presentation was awarded to Karina Chan (right).

The Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS)

The IBICS Mission Statement: The Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS) – is a learned Society engaging a multi-disciplinary community of scientists seeking to advance research that crosses the interface between medicinal inorganic chemistry and biology in Ireland. The Society's mission is to develop, foster and promote a strong national network of scientists collaborating in research areas such as

biology, chemistry, physics and medicine with an interest in biological inorganic chemistry.

The next symposium of the Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS-9) will take place at Maynooth University during the final quarter of 2025, being led by Dr. Diego Montagner. Please see the IBICS website for event updates (<https://ibics.ie>). IBICS welcomes any support for its symposia and the future activities of its members.

Acknowledgements

IBICS-8 was made possible by generous financial support from our sponsors: **Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Institute of Chemistry of Ireland, CRC Press, MSD, CEM, Particular Sciences, Mason Technology, Accuscience, GPE/Julabo, Scientific Laboratory Supplies (SLS)/Ohaus, Medical Supply Company (MSC)**. Many of our sponsors exhibited at the event and contributed to a vibrant meeting.

The local organising committee is grateful to the IBICS Steering Committee for additional support, particularly Luca Ronconi, Diego Montagner, Deirdre Fitzgerald-Hughes, Joseph Byrne, Mick Devereaux, Orla Howe and Celine Marmion. The local committee also thanks our colleagues at UCC for facilitating our hosting of IBICS-8, including Dave Otway for his help with photography.

Figure 6. IBICS-8 local organising committee, from left: Tara McInerney, Rebecca Galway, William Daly, Christopher Burke, Orla Ni Dhubhghaill, Jerry Reen, James Stack.

Previous Events in this Series

- 8th Symposium of the Irish Biological Inorganic Chemistry Society (IBICS-8), University College Dublin, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14052293
- Programmes and event reports for all previous IBICS symposia are available at: <https://ibics.ie/ibics-symposia>